

Clarity of Vision and Its Relationship to the Creative Behavior of NGOs

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Abstract: The study aimed to identify the clarity of vision and its relationship to the creative behavior of Palestinian NGOs in Gaza Strip, and the study used the descriptive analytical approach and the questionnaire as a main tool for collecting data from employees of associations working in the governorates of Gaza Strip, and the cluster sample method was used and the sample size reached (343) individuals. Retrieving (298) questionnaires, and the following results were reached: the relative weight of vision clarity was (79.20%), and the relative weight of creative behavior was (78.99%), a statistically significant relationship between vision clarity and creative behavior, there are significant differences in the visibility due to the gender variable and the differences were in favor of females. There were no statistically significant differences between averages of clarity of vision due to the variable of the age group and the educational qualification, and there were no statistically significant differences in the creative behavior according to the variable of gender, age group, educational qualification, specialization, and the study presented a set of recommendations, the most important of which are: the necessity of seeking civil organizations In Gaza Strip to clarify its vision and to seek financing from external countries in order to provide associations with self-income to face crises and give them independence in order to preserve them to play their role in society. Electronic as it paves the way to reach excellence and creativity in the field of work.

Keywords: Clarity of Vision, Creative Behavior, Palestinian Ngos, Gaza Strip, Palestine.

Introduction

The success of organizations in achieving their goals requires the availability of a number of organizational variables and a sound manner, the most important of which is clarity of vision, as this concept reflects in the organization its personality, as perceived by its employees, and is also a determinant of organizational behavior, as it affects the satisfaction of employees and the level of their performance.

The competitive business environment has undoubtedly increased the speed and rate at which organizations need creativity to maintain their survival and enhance their competitive position. One of the ways in which the organization is creative lies in its ability to enhance, develop, and exploit the talents of employees in particular and their creative potential. The main issue for organizations is how to create the conditions in which organizational members can implement their creative ideas. In this study, the investigation and study will be conducted on the potential inherent in the civil institutions that drive the creative behavior of employees through the clarity of vision of these organizations.

Problem Statement

NGOs face the lack of support and funding sources in Gaza Strip, which requires work to improve the creative behavior of civil society employees, and this requires the use of some modern concepts and strategies to develop their performance. Create and prepare senior management cadres and develop their leadership skills, which requires employees to think in an unfamiliar way to provide creative solutions and recommendations to provide the service in the best possible quality.

Accordingly, the problem of the study revolves around:

What is the relationship between clarity of vision and creative behavior of employees of Palestinian NGOs in Gaza Strip?

Research Objectives

This study aims to achieve the following objectives:

1. Knowing the degree of clarity of vision in NGOs
2. Learn about the creative behavior of NGOs
3. Learn about the nature of the correlation between vision clarity and creative behavior in NGOs.
4. Disclosure of statistical differences from the respondents' answers about (clarity of vision, creative behavior).
5. Providing recommendations and suggestions that may contribute to identifying the best ways to improve the visibility and creative behavior, which in turn may contribute to improving the performance of civil society employees.

Research Importance

The importance of the study can be determined from the contribution and the expected addition from it, as follows:

Applied Importance:

1. The importance of this study stems from the importance of the topic you are discussing, which deals with clarity of vision and its relationship to creative behavior.
2. The availability of this study as a reference in the Palestinian libraries helps researchers in reviewing the results of the study and its recommendations and the possibility of applying similar studies to other samples, or in related fields in creative behavior.

Scientific Importance:

1. The study can assist in providing these recommendations to decision makers and officials in NGOs in order to benefit from them in improving the increase in competitive advantage.
2. Meeting the needs of NGOs to take advantage of the clarity of vision in a way that enhances employee performance and focuses on the importance of creative behavior in NGOs in developing employee performance.

Research hypothesis

In order to provide an appropriate answer to the academic questions raised, the study seeks to test the validity of the following hypotheses:

Ho 1: There is a correlation at (0.05) between the clarity of vision and creative behavior in NGOs.

Ho 2: There are statistically significant differences at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the responses of the sample opinions about clarity of vision according to the following variables (gender, age group, number of years of service, educational qualification and specialization).

This hypothesis is divided into the following subsets of hypotheses:

1. There are statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the responses of the sample opinions on clarity of vision according to the gender variable.
2. There are statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between responses of the sample opinions about clarity of vision according to the age group variable.
3. There are statistically significant differences at the level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the responses of the sample opinions about the clarity of vision according to the variable of the educational qualification.
4. There are statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) level between responses of the sample opinions on clarity of vision according to the specialty variable.
5. There are statistically significant differences at the level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the responses of the sample opinions on clarity of vision according to the variable of the number of years of service.

Ho 3: There are statistically significant differences at the level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the responses of the sample opinions on creative behavior according to the following variables (gender, age group, educational qualification, specialization and number of years of service).

This hypothesis is divided into the following subsets of hypotheses:

1. There are statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the responses of the sample opinions on creative behavior according to the gender variable.
2. There are statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the responses of the sample opinions on creative behavior according to the age group variable.
3. There are statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the responses of the sample opinions on creative behavior according to the variable of the educational qualification.
4. There are statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the responses of the sample opinions on creative behavior according to the specialty variable.
5. There are statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the responses of the sample opinions on creative behavior according to the variable of the number of years of service.

Research Limits and Scope

The scope of the study shall be as follows:

1. **Objective limit:** The issue of clarity of vision and its relationship to the creative behavior of NGOs is addressed.
2. **Spatial limit:** The study was applied to NGOs in Gaza Strip
3. **Time limit:** The study was completed in 2020.
4. **Human limit:** It was applied to all employees in civil organizations according to the conditions set.

Research Terminology

There are many terms that were used in the study, the most important of which are:

- **Creative Behavior:** is represented by what the individual shows in his ability to get rid of the natural context of thinking and follow a new style of thinking, or is it a set of mental characteristics represented by fluency, flexibility and originality or is the emergence of everything that would lead to the production of something new that represents the essence of the interaction between Individual and experience (Hammadat, 2009).
- Procedurally, researchers define it as a set of activities, skills, and feelings a person has that enables them to walk toward creating their own new work unknown to others.

Literature Review

Through examining the researchers a lot of previous studies that relate to the subject of this study to find out the most important topics that were addressed, and to identify the methods and procedures of each study, and the most important results and recommendations reached, and clarify the extent of benefit from them. The researchers presented the previous studies by classifying them according to the chronology from newest to oldest:

- A study of (Hamdan et al., 2020) aimed to identify the creative behavior in the Palestinian civil organizations between reality and expectations, and the study used the descriptive analytical approach and the questionnaire as a main tool for collecting data from employees of associations operating in the governorates of Gaza Strip, and the cluster sample method was used and the sample size was (343) individuals and has been recovered (298) Resolution. The following results were reached: The relative weight of the measure of creative behavior was 78.99 (%), and there were no statistically significant differences in creative behavior according to the gender variable, age group, educational qualification, specialization, while the results indicated that there were differences according to the number of years of service. The study presented a set of recommendations, the most important of which are: the necessity of working to follow up the strategic plan for NGOs using electronic messages as it paves the way for achieving excellence and creativity in the field of work, the need to hold meetings and workshops with the local community and this helps them determine the needs of the community.
- Study of (Alayoubi et al., 2020) aimed to identify the impact of the requirements of implementing strategic entrepreneurship in achieving technical innovation in Palestine Technical College- Deir al-Balah from the point of view of the employees. The researcher used the analytical descriptive method. The study community consists of all academic and administrative staff in the college. The researchers used the comprehensive inventory method. 149 questionnaires were distributed to all members of the study community. The number of questionnaires returned was (115), ie, the response rate was (77.1%). The results of the study showed a strong positive correlation between the requirements of applying strategic entrepreneurship (leadership, pioneering thinking, pioneering culture, strategic resource management) and achieving technical innovation in Palestine Technical College- Deir al-Balah from the point of view of the employees of Palestine Technical College- Deir al-Balah. It also showed a statistically significant effect between the requirements of implementing strategic entrepreneurship (pioneering culture, strategic resource management) and achieving technical innovation in Palestine Technical College- Deir al-Balah, and that the remaining variables show that their effect is weak. The study recommended that the Technical College of Palestine take care of the various requirements of implementing strategic entrepreneurship and develop its organizational capabilities for its direct role in achieving technical innovation of the college.
- Study of (Alayoubi et al., 2020) aimed to identify the strategic leadership practices and their relation to improving the quality of educational service in the Palestinian universities in Gaza Strip. The researcher used the analytical descriptive method. The study population consists of all the supervisors working in three universities in Gaza Strip (The Islamic University, Al-Azhar University, and Al-Aqsa University). A random sample of 177 employees was selected by 50% of the study population. The researcher used the questionnaire as a data collection tool. The results of the study showed a strong and statistically significant relationship between strategic leadership practices (strategic orientation, investment of strategic capabilities and talents, development of human capital, strengthening organizational culture, emphasis on ethical practices, implementation of balanced regulatory control) and improvement of quality of educational service , Responsiveness, safety, empathy) in Palestinian universities. The study recommended that Palestinian universities should take into account the various dimensions of strategic leadership practices and develop their university capacities, including strategic orientation, investment of strategic capabilities and talents, development of human capital, strengthening organizational culture, emphasis on ethical practices and implementation of balanced regulatory control. Educational service for universities.
- A study of (Khoshnood & Nematizadeh, 2017) aimed at explaining the concept of strategic agility and its determinants, revealing its importance in the banking sector and checking its impact on the competitiveness of private banks in Iran, and this study is an applied study, and with regard to data collection it is descriptive and correlative, and it is a society The study consisted of managers and experts working in private Iranian banks, where the study sample reached (150) managers and experts from banks, and the results of the study showed that: strategic agility has a major impact on the competitiveness of private banks in Iran, the dimensions of strategic agility came with mathematical averages passed It also comes of: blurred

vision (4:18) and the selection of strategic goals (4.12) and taking action (3.57) and share responsibilities (3.45) Basic (3.36) and a high capacity ratios.

- Study of (Al-sawaer, 2017) aimed to identify the effect of the intermediate role of business intelligence competencies in the relationship between information technology competencies and organizational agility. This study was applied to the Jordanian commercial banks, which number (13) banks. A suitable sample of (384) individuals from the directors, their deputies, their assistants and heads of general departments in the Jordanian commercial banks in the main departments was appointed. To achieve the purposes of this study, the descriptive analytical approach was used. The results of the study showed: The presence of a statistically significant mediating role for business intelligence competencies (administrative and technical and cultural competencies) in the relationship between information technology and organizational agility in Jordanian commercial banks, and the study showed that the dimensions of the dependent variable (Organizational Agility) has obtained high scores ranging between (4.36-3.63) and its descending order was as follows: the speed of response to customers with a total average of (4.13) and the speed of response to operations with a total average of (4.04) and the speed of response to business partners with an average A total of (3.94), where the ratios indicate that the level of organizational agility is high, and the study recommended the following: Continuing to pay attention to information technology and its capabilities because of its importance reflected on organizational agility in Jordanian commercial banks, spreading the culture of business intelligence and including it in the strategies of commercial banks Jordanian.
- Study of (Ubaidah, 2016) aimed to know the relationship between the organizational climate and the creative behavior of faculty members in intermediate community colleges in Gaza Strip, and the researchers led the accreditation of his study descriptive analytical approach, and the study population consisted of all faculty members in intermediate colleges of Gaza Strip The study sample, which numbered (422) members, was chosen. The study sample represented (50%) of the faculty members in the six intermediate colleges of society chosen for this study. (221) questionnaires were distributed, and a total of (171) were retrieved from them. A questionnaire with a percentage of (77.1%) and a count of The valid questionnaires for the analysis (160) questionnaires, at a rate of (96.5%) from the retriever, all were subjected to statistical analysis, and the study concluded that: there is a statistically significant relationship between the elements of the organizational climate and the creative behavior of its faculty members, the arrangement of the organizational climate elements in terms of their effect on behavior The creativity of faculty members in intermediate community colleges in Gaza Strip as follows: (systems and instructions, participation in decision-making, organizational structure, available technology, working conditions, training, and finally, incentives and rewards), no differences in the focus of the study linked With each of the following personal variables: (age group, educational qualification, number of years of service, type of appointment, and salary), differences in the focus of study are associated with each of the following personal variables (gender, job title, and workplace).
- A study of (Hussein, 2016) that aimed to determine the intermediate impact of strategic agility between environmental sensing strategies and strategic innovation, and in order to achieve this, the types of environmental sensing strategies (closure strategy, gradient strategy, prediction strategy) were adopted based on (Piercy, 2009) and it was adopted Dimensions of strategic agility (strategic sensitivity, strategic response, collective capabilities). While the dimensions of strategic innovation (process innovation, knowledge management) were adopted. Zain Iraq Telecom Company was chosen as a field of research through a questionnaire form that included (154) members from the heads of departments, units and people. Empirical factor analysis (modeling the structural equation) and some descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, simple regression analysis, and multiple gradient regression analysis were used according to what came in selecting the intermediate variable stipulated in a study (Baron & Kenny, 1986). The study results showed that the strategic agility variable partly mediates the relationship between environmental sensing strategies and strategic innovation at the company level. The research sample has a high arithmetic average of (3.236). Such as strategic agility to respond effectively guiding organizations to deal with the total movements in the surrounding environment and include factors flexibility, adaptation and transformation and the transition from one state to another and dealing with environmental developments high smoothly depending on the agility of processes, activities and systems adopted.
- Study of (Jad Allah, 2016) aimed to know the role of school administration in promoting creative behavior among teachers from their point of view, and to develop a proposed concept to enhance the role of school management in developing creative behavior among teachers, and the researcher used the descriptive analytical approach to develop the proposed scenario to enhance the role of management School in developing creative behavior among teachers, and the study population consisted of (4503) male and female teachers, where the study sample was randomly chosen from the study community, but it numbered (350) male and female teachers, and to achieve the goals of the study, the researcher built a questionnaire consisting of (45 paragraphs) Divided into three domain C which are: educational curricula and teaching methods, the school environment, and school activities), and the results of the study indicated: building a proposed concept to enhance the role of school administration in developing creative behavior among secondary school teachers in Gaza governorates, the role of school administration in developing creative behavior among secondary school teachers in governorates Gaza came with a large degree of appreciation and a relative weight (68.20%). There are statistically significant differences between the averages of

the degrees of the individuals of the study sample for the degree of school administration practicing its role in developing creative behavior among secondary school teachers in Gaza governorates, from their point of view attributed to a variable Social type in favor of females, there are no statistically significant differences between the study sample to the degree of school administration for its role in the development of creative behavior among secondary school teachers in Gaza Governorates due to the qualification of scientific variable, and the variable years of service.

- A study of (Abu Radi, 2013), which aimed to know the discovery of the effect of strategic agility on the competitive capabilities in private Jordanian hospitals, and the study attempted to discover this effect through the variables of strategic agility, namely (clarity of vision, understanding the basic capabilities, choosing strategic goals, sharing responsibility, taking Procedures) and competitiveness variables (innovation, service quality, reliability, flexibility, cost leadership), and aimed to examine the extent to which Jordanian private hospitals apply the dimensions of strategic agility, and the study was applied to private Jordanian hospitals located in the capital In order to achieve the goals of this study, the researchers designed a questionnaire consisting of (38) items to collect data from the study sample, which consisted of the departments working in the researched hospitals, where the number of distributed questionnaires reached (233) questionnaires, and the results showed that there is a relationship between the fitness variables The strategy and variables of competitiveness, and that there are differences in the extent of agility in the hospitals examined, and it has also resulted that the hospitals are able to create value and use them in choosing their customers.
- Study of (Al-Mishout, 2011) aimed at identifying the knowledge of the impact of the work environment on administrative creativity at Saad Al-Abdullah Academy for Security Sciences in the State of Kuwait, by using the descriptive analytical approach and the questionnaire as a tool to collect data, and the study reached results that were among the most important The presence of an effect of the organizational structure on administrative creativity, the absence of an effect of regulations and instructions on administrative creativity, an impact of training on administrative creativity, an effect of participation in decision-making on administrative creativity, an effect of incentives and rewards on administrative creativity and a moral impact of technology on administrative creativity, There is a significant effect of working conditions on administrative creativity.
- Study of (Khalaf, 2010) aimed to identify the creation of the relationship between the reality of academic leaders in the Islamic University possessing the attributes and characteristics of the transformative leader and the availability of administrative creativity through identifying the availability of the characteristics of transformational leadership and the study has used the descriptive analytical approach, and the questionnaire as a main tool for data collection The study reached the following results: There is a practice of transformational leadership by academic leaders at the Islamic University of Gaza at a rate equal to (80.6%) and the element (gravity) of the elements of transformational leadership ranked first with a relative weight (82.89%) B The element (intellectual arousal) occupied the fourth rank with a relative weight (79.63%) in the estimates of the sample individuals, and administrative creativity is available among the heads of academic departments at the Islamic University of Gaza with a percentage of (83.94%), and the component (the ability to analyze and link) ranked first with a relative weight (88.33%), while the (acceptance of risk) component ranked seventh with relative weight (80.58). The study also found that there are no statistically significant differences between the respondents' answers about the relationship of transformational leadership to managerial creativity due to demographic and personal variables (age group, number of years of service, and educational qualification).

General Comment on Previous Studies:

By reviewing the previous studies available on the study variables, we can conclude that most studies have dealt with the variables in a way that helps the current study to develop a theoretical and conceptual framework, as well as the conclusion of dimensions and criteria that suit the current study environment, and through the above studies it becomes clear to us the following:

1. Most of the previous studies aimed to clarify the importance of clarity of vision and its important and effective role in making the organization distinguished in its performance.
2. Most previous studies used the descriptive analytical approach as a method for analyzing data.
3. Most of the previous studies relied on the questionnaire to collect data, and some studies relied on the personal interview.
4. In the previous studies, the study sample varied according to the environment in which the study was conducted, and the sample sizes differed according to the target group of the study.

Benefits from Previous Studies:

There are a set of benefits that researchers obtained by reviewing previous studies, and they are as follows:

1. Learn about the latest scientific and research developments in the current field of study.
2. Previous studies have enriched the theoretical side and the framework of thinking the current study.
3. Previous studies also contributed to the formation of a clear perception of the topic (clarity of vision) and the topic of (creative behavior) with their different dimensions and variables.
4. Benefit from the methodology of studies, the sequence of their paragraphs, and the formulation of the current study methodology.

5. Help in designing the study tool (questionnaire)
6. Determine the environment and sample appropriate for the current study.
7. Define the appropriate statistical means for the current study.

What distinguished the current study from previous studies:

The current study was distinguished from other studies at the local level in that it dealt with NGOs, as it is considered the first of its kind according to the researchers' knowledge that links the clarity of vision and creative behavior among the employees of the Palestinian NGOs. It is considered a scientific addition to the Palestinian Library of Theses and Scientific Studies, due to the lack of Arab research trends on the topic of clarity of vision and its important role in keeping pace with events and rapid developments, and therefore the contributions of this study and what distinguishes it from others can be summarized by the scarcity of Arab research that spoke about these two concepts explicitly. On the practical level, Palestinian organizations in general, and international institutions in particular, will benefit from the results of the current study, so that they know the clarity of vision and its relationship to the creative behavior of employees in their organizations, which calls them to pay more attention to visibility. And the need for methods of creative behavior has.

Theoretical Framework

First- Clarity of Vision

Having a clear vision for the organization is the first step in a successful strategic planning, from which the organization extracts its mission, and through which it can set clear goals that the organization seeks to achieve and it answers the most important question for any organization which is what we want to be in the future? Where (Collis & Hussey, 1997) indicated that vision combines insight and sensing, insight indicates a clear picture in the mind, and sensing is the ability to give a mental plan about perceiving events in the future, and after providing clarity of vision the organization provides the speed necessary for implementation and enjoying stability. What is required in investing and exploiting the available opportunities whenever possible, the vision is a realistic process with more attractive credibility for the future, when organizations face complex challenges in light of the environment fluctuating actions provide them with clarity of vision the speed necessary to take decisions and procedures and implement them with the necessary efficiency and focuses on all companies. In its value chain, and pushing it towards exploiting the opportunities associated with it (Wheelen, et al, 2017), he added (Radwan, 2014) that the organization's inability to understand and perceive the reality of its capabilities loses it the ability to exploit these capabilities, which wastes many opportunities, where Clarity of vision provides the organization with the necessary speed for activities and implementation processes and provides motivations for all parties within the value chain that enable them to take advantage of appropriate opportunities.

Requirements for achieving visibility:

There is no doubt that the clarity of vision is not an attribute that any organization can easily possess, but must be supplemented by a set of systematic practices and activities described as requirements in order to maintain the organization's competitive advantages, as he sees both (Chen; et al, 2008), (Beltrame, 2008), (Mackinnon; et al, 2008) as the requirements for clarity of vision are as follows:

1. The need for cooperative relationships between co-employees.
2. The need for the organization to have a database through which it can diversify the sources of information systems.
3. The integration of roles and business across all levels of the organization.
4. The organization has strong leaders.
5. The availability of the necessary social factors related to trust and the balance of power and power between the partners, and trust plays a role in enabling organizations to share knowledge and increases their desire for selection and obtaining more information and data that contribute to its decision-making.
6. Having a flexible organizational structure and improving and developing processes more than expected
7. The organization's ability to define core business, capabilities and processes that enable it to face current and future risks, threats and challenges

Commenting on what was mentioned, the researchers see that one of the most important requirements for clarity of vision is the ability of the organization to determine its basic capabilities, whether human or technical, and develop them better in a way that serves the interest of the organization and gives it the ability to adapt and maneuver and create a distinct value with it with an organizational structure and organizational culture supportive and flexible and participation. In making decisions.

Second - Creative Behavior:

With the advent of the scientific and technological revolution in our time, and the emergence of many administrative difficulties at work, we did not need new and innovative methods to solve our problems. Talking about any organization or ministry working in a society that provides services that are not concerned with the issue of creative behavior of its employees.

There is no doubt that creators play an important and prominent role in human life than what they offer in the future working climate. If we look at the human environment with its visible or invisible aspects, we would find that it is a product of the

imagination of creators in all fields. One faces it in his life, and there is no doubt that it is one of the greatest rewards received in return.

Creative Concept:

It is also known as: "a process similar to scientific research and the process of feeling problems and gaps in information, forming ideas or hypotheses, then testing these hypotheses and modifying them until results are reached." Creativity: the production of a rare, different, and useful new, whether it is thought or action (Al-Surur, 2002).

Creativity and innovation are different synonyms of one meaning, meaning the birth of something new and unfamiliar, or looking at things in new ways (Al-Qaryouti, 2009).

As for creative behavior, it is represented by the individual's ability to get rid of the ordinary context of thinking and to follow a new style of thinking, or it is a set of mental characteristics, the most important of which is fluency, flexibility and originality, or is the emergence of everything that would lead to the production of something new that represents Summary of the interaction between the individual and the experience (Hammadat, 2009).

Consequently, creative behavior becomes: it is the act that precedes creativity, and therefore it does not necessarily result in new or innovative results or services. Rather, it must represent the prevailing and desirable trend in every organization seeking creativity, innovation and excellence. Of course, this action starts from the moment the individual becomes aware The position or circumstance that is the subject of creativity and modernization, and then directly taking care of it, collecting information and data about it, and evaluating the solutions or alternatives available to determine the appropriate alternative, and thus putting it into actual implementation in the field.

But in all cases, the intention of innovation and creativity should be the starting point and the main engine for its existence, because creativity is extremely important in the work of organizations and institutions, it is a basic requirement with the emergence of rapid and continuous fluctuations and the dynamic environment constantly, which requires organizations to provide everything new in the field Practice and application, where creativity helps to enhance the interaction relations between the organization and its environment, and helps it to find solutions to its problems and enables it to face challenges. Also, creativity enables the organization to better invest its human, material and moral resources and continuously maximize its market share, Las As there are many factors that emerge from the organizational climate and significantly affect creative behavior and then creativity, most of which are represented by the following factors (Al-Qatawneh, 2000).

1. Factors related to human resources: These are training opportunities for employees and providing them with new skills that help to change positively, and provide an element of security and job stability, which would enhance confidence and develop the self and provide opportunities for growth and ensure not to engage in resignation or fear of dismissal.
2. Structural factors: It includes the elements of the administrative structure or the organic model that adopts flexibility, decentralization, rapid response and decision-making for the variables of the internal and external environments.

Creativity Elements: Although researchers and experts differ in giving a comprehensive definition of creativity, they all agree that creativity is a capacity that consists of the following elements (Maraj and Abdel Razek, 2006):

1. **Authenticity:** It means the ability to produce unprecedented or unfamiliar ideas, for the creative person possesses original thinking that moves him away from the ordinary or the common.
2. **Fluency:** means the ability to produce a vast amount of ideas that lead directly to the proposed solutions to problems.
3. **Flexibility:** It is the ability to form flexible relationships between things and look at them from different directions.
4. **Tendency to Detail and Analysis:** we mean the ability to understand and analyze the elements that make up things and work to find relationships between these elements.
5. **The Ability to Solve Problems:** This element is the basis of creative work, and we mean by diagnosing many problems within one situation, by defining its dimensions, aspects and shortcomings in it, to reach creative solutions in this regard.
6. **Tendency to Experimentation:** The creative person tends to doubt and criticize the ideas that others consider to be undisputed axioms, as they consider them relativistic and depend on their own perspective.
7. **Self-Confidence:** The creative person is bold and courageous to defend his opinions and ideas, due to his highness in ambition and desire for success.
8. **The Risk:** It means that the creative person is proactive in taking the initiative and adopting new ideas, and at the same time he is ready to assume responsibilities regarding the consequences of this.
9. **Self-Criticism:** The creative person constantly tends to criticize and straighten his ideas using the methods of social and psychological analysis, and not to rely on any image that does not fit with the aspirations aimed at building the human personality, especially with regard to its criticism and evaluation.

Creativity Characteristics: Creativity is characterized by a set of characteristics (Al-Ajez and Sheldan, 2010):

- It requires mental abilities of sensing problems, fluency, originality, flexibility, and continuing towards the goal.
 - A multi-stage process that generates a new idea or business.
 - The effort of creativity and its consequences do not necessarily have to be material tangible. It may be in the form of a specific product, service, idea or vision.
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- It is not an individual phenomenon, but rather can be practiced at the individual, community and institutional level.
- A human being is born with and within him creativity, but it remains latent as he matures within three things: his direction, his behavior and the processes of his thinking.
- It is a human behavior that is not limited to a specific class but rather is a potential energy that is characterized by all individuals in varying degrees, depending on the genetic and objective factors of the circumstances in which the individual lives and interacts with them so that they work to refine their creative capabilities and development.
- Creativity can be managed, developed and developed through basic skills.

The researchers note: From what was mentioned that one of the most important characteristics of creativity is that it is a multiple process that results in a new idea or work and that it is not an individual phenomenon but rather practiced by individuals, society and the organization and that it exists within the person but it remains latent if it does not have the appropriate conditions for its development and it is a human behavior that is not limited to a specific group of people.

Creativity Levels: Many researchers see that creativity is divided into several levels, ranging from organizing life matters to providing creative product that is a breakthrough to custom and out of the ordinary, and distinguishes (Al-Emian, 2005, P: 392-394) between three levels of creativity:

1. Creativity At The Individual Level:

It is creativity that is reached by one of the individuals, and among the characteristics that characterize the creative person: curiosity, perseverance, self-confidence, independence in judgment, self-assertion, intelligence, flexibility, risk-taking, ambition, and ability to analyze, and he addressed many From writers and researchers, this concept searches for features that distinguish the creative personality, which are summarized in (Harem, 2009):

- **Knowledge:** It takes a lot of time for a person to master his work.
- **Education:** which emphasizes that logic hinders creativity.
- **Intelligence:** a creative person is not necessarily highly intelligent, but has the intellectual ability to form flexible relationships between things.
- **Personality:** The creative person loves risk-taking, he is independent, persistent, highly motivated, skeptical, open to new opinions, capable of tolerance, loves coexistence with isolation, and has a great sense of humor.
- **Childhood:** His childhood is diversified, and it is common for him to have faced family troubles and difficult economic situations.
- **Social Customs:** The creative person is not self-introverted, but rather tends to interact and exchange opinions with others.

2. Creativity At The Community Level: It is the creativity that is presented or reached through the group, and the creativity of the group is greater than the individual sum of the creativity of its members, and there is a set of studies that reached the following results regarding the creativity of the group:

- A group that is different in terms of gender produces better solutions than a group in a single gender.
- A cohesive group is more prepared, enthusiastic, and energetic than a less cohesive group.
- That the newly formed group tends to be more creative than the old group.

3. Creativity At The Enterprise Level: It is creativity that is achieved through the collaborative effort of all members of the institution, and studies and research have indicated that creative organizations have the following characteristics:

- The field trend and the tendency to practice and ongoing experimentation despite the failure.
- The presence of supporters and supporters of creativity who encourage and guide creators.
- Productivity through employee participation in making proposals and alternatives to work.
- Simplicity and lack of sophistication in the administrative structure in terms of the number of levels and organizational units.
- Developing principles, values, and ethics for work that everyone knows and works to respect and implement.

Types of Creativity: Some specialists have classified administrative creativity in various organizations as mentioned by (Al-Sultan, 2004) according to the field of creativity with the following:

1. Creativity That Relates To Goals: It includes the goals that the organization wants to achieve.
2. Creativity That Is Linked To the Organizational Structure: it includes rules and tools, procedures, redesign of work, improvement of relations between individuals and interaction between them.
3. Creativity That Relates to the Product or Services: It includes the production of advanced products, and provides new services.
4. Creativity related to customer service and includes a focus on providing services to consumers that exceed their expectations.
5. Innovation that is associated with the process: It focuses on effectiveness, efficiency and flexibility, or includes advanced processes within the organization, including operations and human resource management.

6. Creativity may be radical, leading to tangible changes in the organization, or it may be partly conducive to secondary changes, and it may be pre-planned or may be unplanned.

Stages of the Creativity Process: Creativity is a human phenomenon that takes place according to steps and stages that can be addressed as follows (Harem, 2013):

1. The stage of concern: At this stage the problem that represents the focus of the creative individual's interest is described, so he must ask many questions that he deems necessary to solve this problem. Generally, this stage is the stage of defining the dimensions of the problem and the approved plans.
2. Preparation stage: It consists in collecting information on the subject of the problem, and here creative individuals must develop various methods and specific models of questions and surveys to gather information.
3. Incubation stage: It is a stage in which the interaction between the personality of the researchers and the information and the subject of the research is interacted, as well as the development of solutions and their alternatives.
4. Emerging stage: At this stage the creative individual rearranges and coordinates his thoughts, allowing him to reach a solution, so the latter suddenly flows in the form of creative emergence.
5. Verification stage: In this stage, the sincerity of the new idea reached is tested, that is, whether it is worthy of attention or not. Also here, the creator should think about the mechanism by which the idea can be implemented and the conditions necessary for its success, and who are the persons assigned to implement it.

The sequence of these steps and stages does not represent a model that must be followed, as the creative phenomenon is intertwined and overlapped most of the time, and this does not negate that creative work is carried out according to organized steps, especially at the level of collective creativity, in addition to that it is not always a process that can be controlled and directed according to what serves Objectives of the organization. Often new ideas emerge before they are needed.

Creativity Photos: The most important forms of creativity that organizations work and seek to reach are represented by Peter (2008):

1. Create a new idea, new product, new theory, or new method.
2. Gather old ideas and methods and transform them into a new product or idea.
3. Expand using a new idea, quote or imitate others' experiences.

Researchers note that all types of administrative creativity are closely related to the capabilities, capabilities and attributes of managers, which production and services qualify for production and ensures advanced operations within the organization.

The Relationship between Creativity and Creative Behavior: (Al-Salem, 2014) states that creativity is to present something new that may be represented in a good or service provided or adopted by the institution for the first time. As for creative behavior, it is the distinctive behavior or behavior practiced by the individual or group in the workplace and not necessarily result in results or new services or goods, as it is a behavior that precedes creativity in its final form, and this behavior may be creative in itself when the individual first practices it in the organization.

Meant By Creative Behavior: The researchers define it procedurally: that it is a mixture of features, characteristics, and capabilities possessed by employees in civil organizations in Gaza Strip, which enables them to solve problems, the capacity for communication and risk, and the decision to grant creativity returns in addition to the encouragement and moral support for creativity with all employees to reach the desired goals in the presence of an appropriate correct environment - And researchers also find that the creative behavior of employees, which is an urgent necessity and an essential and effective requirement to overcome the exceptional circumstances surrounding all working conditions.

Creative behavior can be confined to several basic aspects as mentioned (Al-Salem, 2005, P: 95):

1. Creative behavior is a mental ability that can be observed at the level of the individual, group or organization, where these parties are the main axes of creativity.
2. Creative behavior is a production process. The creative process is the ability to create creative production and it appears through physical behaviors or things.
3. The creative process goes through several stages of preparation and maturity until its realization.
4. Creativity can be managed and managed, either by training individuals or groups or providing an environment conducive to creativity for organizations.

The Elements by Which Creative Behavior Is Measured: Creative behavior is measured by several elements mentioned (Al-Salem, 2014):

1. **The Ability to Express:** It expresses the individual's follow-up to new ideas and their development, the desire to enter in non-specialized fields, the ability to change and move from one level to another, and to adapt to the change that may occur in the framework of work.
2. **Brainstorming:** Brainstorming is by searching for all that is new and submitting new proposals and ideas that can be applied on the ground. These new proposals and ideas are encouraged and supported by others, if they are right and of benefit and agreed upon by the majority opinion.

3. **Problem Solving:** It shows the extent of the individual's ability to provide creative solutions to the problems he is going through, and take appropriate measures to solve problems at the appropriate time, in addition to anticipating problems that may occur and try to avoid them, and applying appropriate solutions to them even in the event of scarcity of available information.

The researchers note that measuring the creative behavior of the responsible person is done through the right guidance and distributed to work requirements among employees to find solutions to all that is supposed to be accomplished to the fullest, and harness the climate of capabilities to find appropriate solutions to achieve and achieve the desired goals.

Factors Affecting the Development of Creative Behavior: There are many, many factors that have a direct impact on the development of creative behavior in contemporary and modern institutions. These factors can be summarized as follows: (Al-Salem, 2014) and (Al-Emian, 2005).

1. **Organizational Resilience:** It is the ability of the organization to respond and adapt to the internal and external variables of the business climate.
2. **The Nature of The Work:** Routine actions lead to boredom and lack of creativity, while vital work raises the challenge for the individual and leads him to creative thinking. Several studies have revealed that the degree of challenge provided by the individual's job plays a clear role in influencing the levels of his creativity, provided that the degree of challenge does not exceed the capabilities and capabilities of the individual, which negatively affects his creative behavior.
3. **The Importance of Achievement:** Organizations emphasize achievement and productivity as a basis for material and moral reward.
4. **Characteristics of The Working Groups:** The working groups are defined as including two or more individuals interacting with one another or with whom they have a fixed pattern of relationships and seeking to achieve common goals and consider themselves members of the same group.
5. **The Importance of Development and Training:** where the aspirations of the organization reflect the development of the individual element, which affects the achievement of the goals of the organization through the development of creative capabilities of individuals.
6. **Patterns of Reward and Punishment:** the goal of reward or punishment is to repeat or modify a specific behavior, and reward is given to the creator.
7. **The Degree Of Independence Of The Individual:** Adherence to the prevailing behavioral patterns of others and their imitation in their behavior reduces opportunities for creativity and creativity in the individual, while the tendency to distinguish, independence and lack of commitment to the opinions of others would contribute to developing their creative behavior (Al-Kubaisi, 2017, P: 88).
8. **The Challenge:** where the right man is placed in the right place, in order to practice experience and creative thinking skills, where the manager must be well aware of all the information about workers, and this in turn stimulates the person's underlying motives for creating creative capacity and innovative energy (Al-Laithy, 2008, P: 35-36)
9. **Sources And Resources:** As time and money support creativity, organizations unfortunately routinely kill creativity by adopting a time-limiting policy that makes it impossible to accomplish tasks (Al-Laithy, 2008, P: 35-36)
10. **Climate Environment:** The general atmosphere in the research group is of particular importance, by influencing scientific work, as the appropriate climate allows information to be communicated and exchanged between members of the group, and this climate is fertile soil for finding new ideas or revealing new phenomena through adjustments, mutual monitoring and making corrections with confidence and cooperation. For all ideas and activities presented (Roshka, 1989, P: 78).
11. **Political Factors:** Provides management and political support to transfer creativity processes from the individual level to the level of the organization or society and stimulate the creative energies inherent in the cells of society.
12. **Substantive Factors:** The creativity area covers all aspects of environmental, scientific, administrative, industrial and agricultural life, all of which fall within the possible circle if the degree of ease varies according to the objective nature and the mental, organizational and material capabilities.

From that the researchers conclude that the external and internal influences of the organization are among the most important elements that affect all aspects of the organization, whether it is at the level of the person or the organization, therefore no organization can, when developing its own plans, overlook the issue of multiple and important factors during planning, even if we look at the reality that lives There are organizations in Palestine if they are governmental or non-governmental as a result of the many and many factors that cannot be counted, we see that these organizations are trying to work with everything they can in order to develop and improve performance and present new creative ideas and perhaps there are some success models in this matter despite all the factors To exist in the contemporary reality.

Areas of Creative Behavior: Creative behavior means the life of individuals and gives them the power to produce better for them and for others. It is a lifestyle, a personality trait, and a way to perceive the world. Creative life consists in developing the talents of the individual, and using them in producing different and useful new things. Generally, creative behavior shows the following areas as mentioned (Al- Surur, 2002):

- It develops an individual's ability to derive new ideas and develop sensitivity to others' problems.

- It helps the individual to reach a successful solution to the problem in an original way.
- It is a life skill that an individual exercises daily, and it can be developed through the process of learning and training.
- It contributes to the development of self and creative productions, contributes to developing talents and realizing the world better.
- Makes the person enjoy exploring things themselves.
- It contributes to developing positive attitudes towards solutions to problems and challenges facing individuals in their ordinary lives.
- It leads to being open to new ideas, and responding effectively to opportunities, difficulties and responsibilities to manage risks and adapt to changes.
- It stimulates the tendency to collaborate with others to discover ideas.
- Contributes to developing learning styles and patterns to become more effective.
- It contributes to helping individuals meet their interests and talents.
- It contributes to developing an individual's ability to deal with challenges and life situations in a more creative way
- It contributes to encouraging health institutions and centers to be a suitable environment for discovering talents and promoting their development through the provision of specialized programs.

Pros of Creative Behavior: The positives of creative behavior that leaders provide can be summarized as follows:

- Maintaining enterprise stability.
- Improving administrative organization services to reflect the benefits for the institution and employees.
- Contributing to the development of intellectual and mental capabilities of employees.
- Investing human resources and making use of their capabilities by giving them the opportunity to develop and innovate.
- Raising the efficiency of institutions and their various services.
- Keeping pace with the changing and complex conditions of the work environment for leaders.
- Facing organizational and administrative problems within the organization through change and development.
- Increasing the competitiveness of organizations in light of the fierce competition today.
- Empowering organizations to deal with the needs of globalization
- A way to develop, renew and innovate new methods and solutions to existing problems.

The researchers see from the above: that the employees' leaders in the civil organizations' acquisition of creative behavior makes them able to improve administrative organization services, maintain the organization's stability, develop it, raise its efficiency, and confront administrative and organizational problems within it through continuous development and propose new and innovative solutions to existing problems and future problems.

Creativity Impediments: Creativity is not an easy thing to apply. There are constraints that limit creativity in organizations. The study will talk about two types of these constraints, namely:

First: Personal Obstacles: Personal handicap means those obstacles related to the individual himself, which were developed by him based on his own experiences with his family, school and social environment, the most important of which are the following (Jarwan, 2002):

1. **Weak Self-Confidence:** Self-confidence is an important factor in creative thinking, because poor self-confidence leads to fear of failure and avoids risk and unfamiliar situations and their consequences.
2. **The Tendency to Keep Pace:** The tendency to comply with the prevailing criteria impedes the use of all sensory inputs, limits the possibilities of imagination and expectation, and thus limits the boundaries of creative thinking.
3. **Excessive Enthusiasm:** the individual desire for success and the increased enthusiasm for achieving the results rush to results before the situation matures, and perhaps jump to a later stage in the creative process without exhausting the prerequisite that may require a longer time.
4. **Saturation:** Saturation means reaching a state of excessive absorption that may lead to a decrease in awareness of the status quo, and the inaccuracy of observations.
5. **Modular Thinking:** Typical thinking means that type of thinking, usually restricted.
6. **Lack of Sensitivity or Feeling Powerless:** an essential characteristic of creative thinking is alertness and delicate sensitivity to problems. And when sensitivity weakens, as a result of lack of excitement or lack of challenge, the person becomes more inclined to stay in the circle of reactions to what is going on around him, and gives up the initiative to explore the dimensions of the problem and engage in finding solutions to it merely feeling it.

7. **Hastiness and The Possibility of Ambiguity:** This characteristic is related to the desire to find an answer to the problem by seizing the first opportunity without absorbing all aspects of the problem, and working to develop several alternatives or solutions to it, and then the best.

Second: Organizational Obstacles

The organizational obstacles that hinder creativity are many; the most important of them are:

- Literal adherence to laws, instructions, and procedures.
- Lack of confidence in some managers of themselves and employees.
- Unhealthy organizational climate.
- Lack of qualified administrative leadership.
- Implementing an improper organizational structure that does not allow individuals freedom of opinion, diligence, disposition and judgment.
- Mismanagement of the conflict and the organization's political map.
- Improper administrative procedures, including leadership, decision-making, communications, and others.
- Lack of necessary resources.
- Lack of support and support for creativity and initiative, and the selection of new ideas and solutions.

As for (Al-Surur, 2002), it stated that the obstacles to creativity are:

- Environmental constraints: noise, overcrowding, overcrowding, unavailability
- Financial support.
- Cultural barriers: such as society's rejection of creative ideas, criticism of creative ideas.
- Cognitive visual barriers: such as using a sense alone in thinking, seeing a person's visual on one side, neglecting the rest of the sides, not using all the sensory inputs.
- Expressive barriers: such as the inability to communicate ideas to others and themselves, using inappropriate intellectual methods, incorrect information or lack of information.
- Intellectual barriers: such as using inflexible and incorrect ideas, identifying ideas needed for a specific age and time.
- Cognitive barriers: such as the stereotypical view of things, rigidity of opinion, the tendency to restrict the problem, isolate the problem and not look at it from different perspectives.
- Emotional (emotional) handicaps: such as being unable to tolerate ambiguity, fear of making a mistake.
- Subliminal and subconscious impediments to new ideas, from the ideal ego, and it is feared to punish society for these ideas, and these ideas remain locked up to the supreme I, and this conflict leads to nervous debility.
- Time constraints (the historical era): creative achievements that were not appreciated during their owners, but the community valued them after their death, and time here affects the amount of creativity, the type of creativity, and the nature of community evaluation.
- Other constraints: such as lack of information, lack of background on creativity, lack of encouragement for individuals to productivity, failure to exploit an individual's capabilities and senses, lack of discussion, mockery and irony, and lack of appreciation for work.

The researchers note that the obstacles to creative behavior of employees in civil organizations lie in the lack of material and human capabilities they have, the lack of sufficient will to make decisions in the scope of their work, and the low interest of the high leadership in them and their strengthening by them.

Dimensions of Creative Behavior:

Studies and research that dealt with creative behavior varied in terms of its dimensions. Some of them mentioned that the dimensions of creative behavior are represented in five dimensions such as the study (Al-Ahmad, 2008) represented in:

The First Dimension: exploring opportunities.

The Second Dimension: creating ideas.

The Third Dimension: verification.

Fourth Dimension: The Challenge.

Fifth Dimension: the follow-up card.

As for the study (Mahdi, 2012) that dealt with creative behavior, its dimensions were represented in four dimensions:

The First Dimension: Creative Problem Solving: The ability to feel problems is an essential component of creative work, and we mean by it (Mohamed, 2010, P: 8) to diagnose many problems within a single situation, by identifying their dimensions, aspects and deficiencies in order to reach creative solutions regarding them, as well as fluency, which means the ability to Produce a vast amount of ideas that lead directly to the proposed solutions to problems.

The Second Dimension: Communication Capacity: Communication capacity in administrative work is an administrative function that relates to its nature, and means communication, communication and the exchange of ideas and meanings and with the aim of creating certain behaviors.

- **Listening:** that is, the manager listens to his employees in order to discover the truth of what the employee wants to say.
- **Explanation:** That is, the manager must explain his ideas to be influential in his employees.
- **Question and Discussion:** That is, before determining the purpose of the communication.
- **Evaluation:** It is useful as a method of control and motivation as it helps to perform and work to improve it.
- **Response:** The manager's note of the position requirements.

It is worth noting that Palestinian NGOs are striving since their establishment to strengthen the relationship between all employees and improve the language of communication and communication between different categories of employees, and seek to enter modern means of communication such as computers and follow e-mail as an alternative to paper communications in order to advance the work of organizations and keep pace with the rapid technological and scientific development.

The Third Dimension: Risk: The risk as mentioned (Rafik, 2010) is considered one of the elements of creative behavior, and it means that the creative director is a race to take the initiative and adopt new ideas, and at the same time is ready to assume responsibilities regarding the consequences of this, and the leader's behavior in itself is one of the main factors that increase The motivation of employees towards work and raising their morale so that they can face the problems that hinder them from working, as it is not reasonable for the leader to think creatively while still clinging to the old and does not have a spirit of risk towards change, but he must be himself renewed thinking and cultivate a spirit of positive competition Among his employees In order to push them to new ideas and discuss them with them while lending a helping hand to them, and the effective leader is bold and courageous in nature, he sometimes takes risks, while bearing all the consequences of that.

The Fourth Dimension: Encouragement and Moral Support for Creativity: (Al-Salem, 2005) mentioned that the organizational climate is an essential element for establishing creativity and its system, which has positive effects in increasing creativity within the organization, and the creative opportunity is to provide and create a creative and cognitive climate and develop creativity for all employees at all levels, while The development and development of creative human resources to make them more capable of managing the organization by making them more creative by raising morale and maintaining, developing and developing human resources within the organization.

By examining the researchers on many studies and research that touched on creative behavior, he extracted a set of practices practiced by employees in civil organizations and helps them to creativity by motivating and encouraging employees to come up with creative ideas and behaviors and providing moral and material support to them and encouraging a spirit of competition among employees in organizations to push them towards Reaching new creative ideas in order to improve their work and achieve the goals of the organization, and keeping pace with the new changes on the ground in mind is necessary and natural, and adapting to them, setting solutions to them and dealing with a new method of communication and communication With the employees to discuss and explain their ideas to reach the desired result in the discussion and give an opportunity to others in the discussion and not boycott it so that he can clarify his point of view and spread a culture that accepts the other and work in a team spirit. Safe from the fear of error, it must be sown in all employees that it is okay to make mistakes, the important thing is to learn from it something new every time, and work to develop self-confidence and provide educational experiences to develop a sense of responsibility and care to strengthen and develop the internal motives for achievement, excellence and freedom On the participation of subordinates at work in the evaluation and decisions for adopting and encouraging experimentation and ways and methods are diverse and creative.

The researchers note: When it comes to employees of organizations, the administrative dimension of strategic leadership becomes increasingly important and becomes a critical requirement for the fundamental success in achieving the desired goals in the organized work in its various aspects. An administrative work based on the administrative aspects that must be adequately met by enough employees in this field, which requires an administrative leader promotes these management practices to achieve advancement in the organization.

Given the difficult and complex conditions in which Palestinian NGOs operate and which pose great and varied challenges and urgent matters that were not taken into account, therefore it is imperative for decision makers in NGOs to confront such conditions by creating strategic managers who are characterized by skills, competencies and creative capabilities and have the ability to adopt the most appropriate solutions and ideas. That enables organizations to progress towards the best and continue to provide services with great effectiveness, and employees must distinguish with creative capabilities and adopt creative behavior among employees in Palestinian civil organizations.

The Relationship between Clarity of Vision and Creative Behavior: The clarity of vision is considered one of the most essential requirements for the success of organizations and ensuring their continuity in Gaza governorates, which need ingenuity to work to obtain financial support to support the sector in all forms, which is done through the application of clarity of vision in NGOs to be able to have a new vision to know its location among competitors among other organizations.

Employees have an important role in developing the organization's ability to define its various goals in order to obtain those projects in all ways and means, in a manner that best serves the interest of society and the organization together and gives it the ability to adapt and maneuver and create its distinctive value by organizing its organizational structure and supporting it in all ways and involving employees in making decisions related to the organization, including flexibility in work, which is concerned with managing predictable change and working in all ways that improve the performance of its employees, since the clarity of vision is concerned with speed and rapid response to internal and external changes, in order to erase a sign of its survival, guarantee and continuity in providing various services and access to achieving creative behavior at work practiced by employees with every professionalism to develop their creativity within NGOs working in Gaza Strip, and this was confirmed by a study (Al-sawaer, 2017) that emphasized the importance of the relationship between strategic agility and creativity in light of technology business. As well as a study (Al-Abedi and Al-Musawi, 2014) that emphasized the role of the relationship between strategic intelligence indicators to ensure strategic sovereignty through agility of the strategic movement, measuring the creative behavior of employees in NGOs operating in Gaza Strip and also harnessing the appropriate organizational climate for work for employees and providing possibilities of finding appropriate solutions to accomplish and achieve the desired goals, which are considered one of the most important factors affecting all aspects of work within NGOs, whether at the individual or organization level, by setting the basic and important factors and conditions during planning.

The organizations strive to work with all their creative energies in order to develop and improve performance and provide new creative ideas that are in line with the work of organizations operating in Gaza Strip, and to provide employees with creative behavior, which makes them able to improve work services and administrative organization and maintain the stability and development of the organization and raise its efficiency and confront administrative and organizational problems inside it through continuous development and proposing new and innovative solutions to the existing problems and future problems, which since its inception strive to consolidate the relationship between all its employees and improve the language of communication and communication between groups of various aspirations, as well as developing various methods to introduce modern means of communication such as computers and follow e-mail as an alternative to paper-based communications in order to advance the work of organizations and keep pace with the rapid scientific and technological development, by having sufficient experience to work in light of the deteriorating and unstable economic conditions and the ability to speak the language that public opinion understands the world and the local through their complex relations with many parties and influential in their societies, to obtain support in all forms.

It is necessary to expand the margin of active participation and urge it to improve the work of civil organizations operating in Gaza Strip, which have proven the results of the current study on the importance of the relationship between strategic agility and creative behavior and work to spread awareness among employees about the necessity of their participation in assessing, identifying and developing the services provided in a manner commensurate with the work of NGOs.

Through what has been mentioned, the researchers conclude that the most important elements of the success of any civil or non-governmental organization is the presence of wise leaders, who are able to achieve their desired goals, and lead their employees in a positive manner and creative behavior that represents an example for others, and perhaps strategic leadership is the most capable of achieving these meanings in the organization, especially the NGOs in Palestine, which need this type of leadership.

NGOs:

During the 1980s, NGOs were formed working in the fields of learning, health, development, agriculture, etc. This rapid growth of new civil institutions, led by young and professional groups, has also contributed to important transformations in some typical charitable societies, in terms of their orientations and areas of work, some of which have initiated the creation of universities, hospitals, training and employment centers, industrial and agricultural lending, and some generating projects income based on lunch and handicraft production (Halila, 1999, p: 23).

The challenge before the Palestinian civil organizations remains in their ability to reproduce themselves socially, and in their active and serious involvement in the political process to defend the interests of the groups they represent and to contribute to the democratization of the Palestinian society and political system, in continuing to perform their national role and activate it in resisting and defeating the occupation through various forms and activities and in areas that the National Authority and its institutions may be unable to work in because of the agreements concluded and the obligations that they have placed on their obstacles.

And based on the foregoing, these organizations will continue to be unable to carry out these tasks and play their roles efficiently and effectively, unless a process takes place evaluating their administrative and organizational structures, their performance, their methods of work and their relationship, and on top of all this is strengthening their intra-democratic structure, adherence to the principles of transparency and accountability, and activating the voluntary and public side in their work and its programs, and to enhance coordination, integration, cooperation and networking relations with relevant authorities.

The New Development Vision in the Work of Palestinian Ngos: Within the political changes, the civil work organizations have developed a clear and realistic vision of the nature of their goals and programs during the current stage, and they have reached a

precise and deep understanding of their roles at this stage, especially their relationship with the Palestinian Authority, on the one hand, and Palestinian society on the other hand, and this vision was based on the following national components:

1. Serious, real and effective contribution to resisting the Israeli occupation on the one hand, and building an independent and democratic Palestinian state on the other.
2. Contributing to building a democratic Palestinian society where the emergence of the Palestinian National Authority has generated new requirements, requirements and roles for civil work, the most important of which is defining the content of the relationship between the state on the one hand and the Palestinian individual on the other hand and civil society on the third side, as well as the relationship of civil society with the private sector on the fourth hand.

It is the duty of civil work organizations to contribute effectively to building a strong and capable civil society based on governance and the rule of law, and civil society cannot be effective without regulating its relations with the National Authority, especially at the level of the development framework that is based on working national development policies that respond to the interests of The priorities of the local community, in addition to this, the development process cannot take place or achieve clear achievements without real development on the institutional organizational level of Palestinian political institutions or their ministries and technical institutions and the reform process, just as civil society cannot be built democratically, without defending the rights of vulnerable and marginalized groups, and ensuring their interests and their political, economic, social and legal rights within the framework of a comprehensive strategic plan to combat poverty, this plan is extremely important, especially in the current stage where poverty rates increase at an accelerated rate, and Palestinian citizens are exposed to economic measures in The difficulty.

Reasons for Caring For Ngos: The countries of the world are interested in NGOs for several reasons. These reasons reinforce the importance of NGOs in the development process, and among these reasons (AL-Nabahen, 2008, P: 54-55):

- It reflects a social development need, usually created within local communities, and thus is the natural or spontaneous response to the social development needs of a specific group, group, segment of the population, geographic region, political trend, or social issue.
- The ability to move relatively freely, as it is relatively free from governmental and official determinants in many aspects, including political and administrative aspects.
- Communication and communication with the targeted groups, and depending on their structure, popular nature and volunteer component, NGOs are usually better able to reach and communicate with the target groups.
- Being more receptive and having greater confidence by the target groups, depending on the high degree of contact and communication with the target groups, the organizations usually have more confidence by these groups and thus dealing with greater positivity.
- Movement flexibility. NGOs usually have a high relative flexibility of movement. Especially because it is more liberal than the determinants of bureaucracy that governments suffer from.

Methodology and Procedures:

The study methodology and procedures are considered a major axis through which the applied side of the study is accomplished, and through it the data required to perform the statistical analysis to reach the results that are interpreted in the light of the literature related to the subject of the study, and thus achieve the goals that it seeks to achieve.

As well as the study tool used and the method of preparation and how to build and develop it, and the extent of its sincerity and consistency, and the chapter ends with the statistical treatments that were used in analyzing the data and extracting the results, and the following describes these procedures.

First - The Study Methodology: The study used the descriptive analytical method that relies on description, analysis and correlative comparison with the aim of describing what is an object, and its interpretation by highlighting the problem of the study to be researched and a close understanding of its conditions, and collecting information that increases the clarification of the conditions surrounding the problem.

The Researchers Used Two Primary Sources Of Information:

1. **Secondary Sources:** Where the researchers moved in addressing the theoretical framework of the study to secondary data sources, which are represented in the relevant Arab and foreign books and references, periodicals, articles, reports, and previous research and studies that dealt with the subject of study, research and reading in various internet sites.
2. **Primary Sources:** To address the analytical aspects of the subject of the study, the researchers resorted to collecting primary data through the questionnaire as a main tool for the study, specially designed for this purpose.

Second - The Study Community: The study community is defined as all the vocabulary of the phenomenon that researchers study, and based on the study problem and its goals, the study community is represented by employees in charitable societies operating in Gaza Strip of various types (local and international), provided that:

- That at least 5 years have passed since its establishment, until the organization is established and its areas of work are clear.

- That the number of its employees be 8 or more, so that there is an administrative process applied to the employees and can be studied.
- That the association's expenses during a year be more than 2,000,000 shekels, in order to have an impact on society.
- That the organization has existing projects to be implemented in recent months.
- The percentage of the governorate from the total number of organizations in all the governorates of the sector.

According to the following schedule:

Table 1: Study Population and Sample

No.	Governorate	Number Of Associations	Number Of Employees	Sample Number
1.	North of Gaza Strip	7	350	38
2.	Gaza	30	1831	198
3.	Central of Gaza Strip	4	458	50
4.	Khan Younes	6	425	46
5.	Rafah	1	103	11
Total		48	3167	343

Source: General Department of Public Affairs and NGOs in the Ministry of Interior: 2020

Consequently, the study population consists of 48 associations with 3,167 employees, distributed over the five governorates of Gaza Strip.

Third - The Study Sample: The cluster sample method was used because there are differences between charitable societies in different governorates due to the difference in the nature of the activity of each association and the services that it provides to the public. The study sample size reached (343), and 298 employees responded to them.

The following table shows the distribution of respondents according to the study variables:

Table 2: Distribution of respondents according to personal data

Gender	Male		Female		Total	
	147		151			298
Age Group	Less than 30 years old	30 - Less than 40 years old	40- Less than 50 years old	50 years and over	298	
	107	119	50	22		
Qualification	Diploma below		Bachelor's Degree	Postgraduate	298	
	62		188	48		
Specialization	Human Sciences	Administrative And Financial Sciences	Engineering Sciences	Public Relations And Media	Other Specialties	298
	94	87	23	21	73	
Number of Years of Service	Less than 5 years	From 5 to 10 years	From 10 to 15 years old	Over 15 years old	298	
	95	84	59	60		

Fourth- Study Tool: A questionnaire has been prepared on "clarity of vision and its relationship to the creative behavior of NGOs", which consists of three main sections:

The First Section: It is the personal data of the respondents (gender, age group, educational qualification, specialization, number of years of service).

The Second Section: visibility

Section Three: Creative Behavior

Visibility Scale Description:

The scale consists of (21) phrases, which measure and the following table:

Table 3: The distribution of paragraphs of the visibility scale over the various fields

No.	Field	Paragraphs Number
1.	Clarity Vision	6
2.	Creative Behavior	15

Section Two: The Creative Behavior Scale

Rationing Stage: Includes validity and reliability calculation for the test.

1. The validity of the arbitrators:

The scale was presented in its current form to a number of arbitrators with specialists from business administration professors, who are (13), to identify the appropriateness of the test phrases and their representation of the aspects that are included in them. Validity of scale for application.

2. Validity of the building using the internal consistency method:

The scale was applied to a survey sample of (32) from the original community members of the study. Correlation coefficients were calculated for each paragraph in the domain to which it belongs, as well as correlation coefficients between domains with each other. All paragraphs got a level of significance of 0.05. This indicates that the scale is characterized by a high degree of honesty of the internal consistency.

Table 4: Correlation coefficient between each of the paragraphs after "visibility" and the total degree of the dimension

No.	Paragraphs	R	Sig.
1.	The vision and overall goals of the organization are realistically formulated.	.866	0.01
2.	Workers have clarity about the organization's vision and value.	.905	0.01
3.	The organization is proud of what it is trying to achieve within the overall business units.	.889	0.01
4.	Comprehensive planning that clarifies the organization's goals and future vision is encouraged.	.912	0.01
5.	The organization has a high level of agreement on principles guiding its behavior.	.920	0.01
6.	New ideas that bring about the organization's full vision are presented.	.812	0.01

Table 5: Correlation coefficient between each paragraph of the "creative behavior" scale and the overall scale of the scale

No.	Paragraphs	R	Sig.
1.	The organization works with workers to take decisions to encourage creative behavior in it.	.824	0.01
2.	Studies are conducted on organized business development methods and divisions.	.732	0.01
3.	I believe in generating and applying new ideas to work within the organization.	.725	0.01
4.	I practice the techniques of some distinguished colleagues to develop my business skills.	.609	0.01
5.	I have the ability to anticipate business problems before they happen	.595	0.01
6.	The organization allocates the funds needed to implement innovative projects and ideas.	.624	0.01
7.	The official encourages the creative ideas presented by the workers of the organization.	.854	0.01
8.	I have the ability to refuse the wrong instructions and procedures.	.581	0.01
9.	Bring new ideas without hesitation and fear that they will fail.	.704	0.01
10.	Adapt to variables in the work environment smoothly and flexibly.	.551	0.01
11.	Perform the work assigned to in a sophisticated manner.	.762	0.01
12.	Technology is used to increase contact with workers inside and outside the organization.	.589	0.01
13.	The organization rewards the owners of distinguished production.	.734	0.01
14.	The organization urges workers to acquire creative skills	.754	0.01
15.	I use my personal relationships to communicate with outside parties and obtain material and moral gains for the organization.	.395	0.05

Stability of Scale:

The researchers checked the stability of the scale on a polling sample of (32) employees. The stability of the scale was calculated using the two half-hash methods, and Cronbach's coefficient alpha.

1. Split-Half Method:

The correlation coefficient was calculated between the sum of the even terms and the sum of the individual expressions for the test and its domains, using the Spearman Brown equation and the stability coefficients were all high, indicating that the scale had a high degree of stability. The following table shows that:

Table 6: shows the coefficient of stability of the scale of visibility by the half-way method

No.	The Scale	The Number Of Paragraphs	Correlation Coefficient Before Modification	Correlation Coefficient After Adjustment	Significance Level
1.	Clarity Vision	6	0.893	0.943	0.01
2.	Creative Behavior	15	0.778	0.874	0.01

2. Cronbach's coefficient alpha method:

A stability coefficient was calculated for all scale fields, and the following table shows this:

Table 7: Cronbach's coefficient alpha for each Scale Field

No.	The Scale	Coefficient of stability
1.	Clarity Vision	0.942

2.	Creative Behavior	0.894
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It is clear from the previous table that all stability parameters are statistically significant, confirming the validity of the scale for application.

Data Analysis, Study Hypotheses, and Discussion

It includes an offer to analyze data and test the hypotheses of the study, by answering the study questions and reviewing the most prominent results of the questionnaire, which was reached through the analysis of its paragraphs, and to find the personal data of the respondents, so statistical treatments were made for the data collected from the study questionnaire, as the packages program was used. Statistical for Social Studies (SPSS) to obtain the results of the study that was presented and analyzed.

Statistical description of the study sample according to personal data

The following is a presentation of the characteristics of the study sample according to personal data

Table 8: Distribution of the study sample according to personal data

Personal Data		Count	Percentage%
Gender	Male	147	49.3
	Female	151	50.7
	Total	298	100.0
Age Group	Less than 30 years	107	35.9
	30 - Less than 40 years	119	39.9
	40- Less than 50 years	50	16.8
	50 years and over	22	7.4
	Total	298	100.0
Qualification	Diploma below	62	20.8
	Bachelor's Degree	188	63.1
	Postgraduate	48	16.1
	Total	298	100.0
Specialization	Human Sciences	94	31.5
	Administrative And Financial Sciences	87	29.2
	Engineering Sciences	23	7.7
	Public Relations And Media	21	7.0
	Other Specialties	73	24.5
	Total	298	100.0
Number Of Years Of Service	Less than 5 years	95	31.9
	From 5 to 10 years	84	28.2
	From 10 to 15 years old	59	19.8
	Over 15 years old	62	20.1
	Total	298	100.0

It is clear from the previous table that 49.3% of the study sample is male, while 50.7% of females, as this result differs relatively with the statistic of the Palestinian Statistics Center for the year 2018, which showed that the percentage of male participation in strength in institutions is four times the rate of participation Females, and the relative difference is noted here, where the female participation rate increases compared to the aforementioned Palestinian labor market, and researchers attribute this to the nature of employment laws in civil organizations as it enhances the opportunities for females to obtain jobs, and allows them more opportunities, especially in women's projects, as well as due to the nature of many Of jobs and tasks in aphids Local times to suit the female nature.

And that 75.8% of the sample of the study are young people under the age of 40 years and the rest of the proportion is from the older age group, it is clear from the table the largest percentage is for those under the age of 40, which is a very good percentage of young people who work in administrative jobs within the civil organizations The researchers attribute this to the presence of young

elements in the Palestinian society capable of leading and advancing these organizations, and the presence of a strong trend within the organizations by relying on modern technology, cultural and intellectual exchanges between peoples and the spread of social media platforms, which are definitely mastered by this age group with high professionalism. Able to overcome and overcome the difficulties faced by organizations, as there is a clear decrease in the category Alamrahah category greater than 50 years experience confirms diminishing element for the benefit of technical expertise and modern scientific.

And that 63.1% of the study sample hold a bachelor’s degree, while 20.8% of the diploma holders while 16.1% of the graduate studies holders, and this is consistent with the fact that working in private institutions in Gaza Strip requires a bachelor’s degree mainly. The researchers attribute that the number of the diploma degree holders is small and the trend towards a bachelor’s degree, which focuses on administrative jobs and tasks in civil organizations, and such jobs certainly have requirements and tasks that are not often less than a bachelor’s degree, which explains the high percentage of bachelor’s degree holders in the sample, The percentage of holders of postgraduate degrees is also low for undergraduate degrees, which are included with the researchers’ interpretation of the nature of administrative tasks, and the ability to make decisions, develop strategic plans and lead the teams according to a calculated scientific approach.

It is also clear that 31.5% of the study sample is a graduate of the humanities (education and arts), while 29.2% are graduates of administrative and financial sciences and 7.7% of graduates of engineering disciplines while 7% of graduates of public relations and media and the rest of the proportion are from other disciplines. The researchers attribute that the fields of work in the Palestinian civil institutions need to diversify in scientific disciplines, and this comes to the disciplines of human sciences and administrative specialties that supervise activities with human specialties, engineering, public relations, and other specializations come at a lower rate due to the services provided by NGOs in Gaza Strip that It is dominated by services, humanitarian and relief in line with the projects presented by these organizations.

And that 31.9% of the study sample had less than 5 years of experience, while 28.2% of their experience duration was 5-10 years, and 20.1% of their experience duration was more than 15 years while 19.8% of their experience duration was 10 -15 years. The researchers clarify from the proportions that the largest percentage went to holders of the number of years of service less than 5 years, and the researchers attribute this to the nature of the study community, as the administrative functions and tasks assigned to employees in associations in Gaza Strip directly depend on rapid knowledge in the rapid technological development and mixing with the cultures of the world, and the acquisition of experiences in Short years, enables a person to be able to make appropriate decisions and accomplish the required tasks in the organization more effectively and efficiently, depending on previous experience.

The Criterion Approved In the Study

To determine the criterion adopted in the study, the length of the cells was determined in the Likert pentatonic scale by calculating the range between the scale grades (5-1 = 4) and then dividing it by the largest value in the scale to obtain the length of the cell i.e. (4/5 = 0.80) and then This value was added to the lowest value in the scale (the beginning of the scale and it is the correct one) to determine the upper limit of this cell, and thus the length of the cells became as shown in the following table (Ozen et al., 2012):

Table 9: It shows the criterion approved in the study

SMA	Relative Weight	Degree Of Approval
From 1- 1.80	From 20% - 36%	Strongly Disagree
From 1.80- 2.59	From 36%- 51.99%	Not Agree
From 2.60- 3.39	From 52%- 67.99	Neutral
From 3.40- 4.19	From 68%- 83.99%	Agree
From 4.20 - 5	From 84%- 100%	Strongly Agree

To explain the results of the study and judge the level of response, the researchers relied on the arrangement of arithmetic averages at the level of areas for the questionnaire and the level of paragraphs in each field, and the researchers have determined the degree of approval according to the criterion approved for the study.

Answer To Study Questions:

The result of the first question: Which states: What is the level of clarity of vision among civil servants?

The mean, standard deviation, relative weight, order, and degree of approval were used. The results are shown in the following table:

Table 10: Arithmetic mean, standard deviation, relative weight, and ranking for each of the paragraphs after "clarity of vision"

S.N.	Paragraph	SMA	Standard Deviation	Relative Weight	Ranking	Degree of Approval
1.	The vision and overall goals of the organization are realistically formulated.	4.03	758.	80.60%	1	Agree
2.	Workers have clarity about the organization's vision and value.	3.89	869.	77.80%	6	Agree

3.	The organization is proud of what it is trying to achieve within the overall business units.	4.01	823.	80.20%	2	Agree
4.	Comprehensive planning that clarifies the organization's goals and future vision is encouraged.	3.96	757.	79.20%	3	Agree
5.	The organization has a high level of agreement on principles guiding its behavior.	3.96	869.	79.20%	4	Agree
6.	New ideas that bring about the organization's full vision are presented.	3.93	850.	78.60%	5	Agree
Total Score		3.9600	61361.	79.20%		Agree

From the previous table, the following can be concluded:

The arithmetic mean for the first paragraph "is formulated to see the organization and its general objectives with realism" equal to 4.03 (total score of 5), meaning that the relative weight is 80.60%, and this means that there is high approval by the sample members of this paragraph.

The researchers attribute this to: that civil organizations in Gaza Strip put forward plans to develop a clear vision, mission and clear appropriate goals in line with the institution's goals and clarity of goals for the targeted groups as well as taking appropriate strategic decisions that support the institution in its progress and advancement at all levels.

The mean for the second paragraph "The employees have a clarity of the organization's vision and value" is equal to 2.89, meaning that the relative weight is 77.80%, and this means that there is high approval by the sample members of this paragraph.

The researchers attribute this to the fact that civil organizations in Gaza Strip fall under the administrative control of the interior and implement what they are required to do, such as monitoring reports and projects implemented by institutions in Gaza Strip

In general, it can be said that the mean of the dimension of clarity of vision "equals 3.96, meaning that the relative weight is 79.20%, and this means that there is a high agreement by the members of the sample on the paragraphs of this dimension.

The researchers attribute this to the fact that organizations in Gaza Strip always strive to clearly define the vision and objectives in order to compete with other institutions and obtain financial support for projects that will be implemented through the financiers and benefit from them and serve the community in light of the blockade imposed on Gaza Strip.

The result of the second question: Which states, "What is the degree of application of creative behavior in Palestinian NGOs according to the opinions of the sample?"

To answer the question, the mean, standard deviation, relative weight and order were used to find out the degree of approval. The results are shown in the following table:

Table 11: Arithmetic mean, standard deviation, relative weight and rank for each of the "creative behavior" paragraphs

S.N.	Paragraph	SMA	Standard Deviation	Relative Weight	Ranking	Degree of Approval
1.	The organization works with workers to take decisions to encourage creative behavior in it.	3.87	980.	77.40%	12	Agree
2.	Studies are conducted on organized business development methods and divisions.	3.89	893.	77.80%	11	Agree
3.	I believe in generating and applying new ideas to work within the organization.	4.10	852.	82.00%	4	Agree
4.	I practice the techniques of some distinguished colleagues to develop my business skills.	4.16	783.	83.20%	1	Agree
5.	I have the ability to anticipate business problems before they happen	4.02	831.	80.40%	7	Agree
6.	The organization allocates the funds needed to implement innovative projects and ideas.	3.91	900.	78.20%	10	Agree
7.	The official encourages the creative ideas presented by the workers of the organization.	3.95	901.	79.00%	9	Agree
8.	I have the ability to refuse the wrong instructions and procedures.	3.96	883.	79.20%	8	Agree
9.	Bring new ideas without hesitation and fear that they will fail.	4.08	721.	81.60%	5	Agree
10.	Adapt to variables in the work environment smoothly and flexibly.	4.14	666.	82.80%	3	Agree
11.	Perform the work assigned to in a sophisticated	4.27	622.	85.40%	1	Agree

S.N.	Paragraph	SMA	Standard Deviation	Relative Weight	Ranking	Degree of Approval
	manner.					
12.	Technology is used to increase contact with workers inside and outside the organization.	4.06	857.	81.20%	6	Agree
13.	The organization rewards the owners of distinguished production.	3.69	1.067	73.80%	14	Agree
14.	The organization urges workers to acquire creative skills	3.85	992.	77.00%	13	Agree
15.	I use my personal relationships to communicate with outside parties and obtain material and moral gains for the organization.	3.41	1.252	68.20%	15	Agree
Total Score		3.949	55644.	78.99%		Agree

From the previous table, the following can be concluded:

The arithmetic mean for the fourth paragraph, "I practice the methods of some distinguished colleagues to develop my skills at work." It equals 4.27 (total score of 5), i.e. the relative weight of 85.40%, which means that there is high approval by the sample members of this paragraph.

The researchers attribute this to the interest of the owners of associations in the Gaza Strip to have a distinguished management team capable of keeping abreast of developments in order to practice their work with professionalism and professionalism in light of keeping pace with technological developments.

The mean of the fifteenth paragraph "I use my personal relationships to communicate with external parties and obtain material and moral gains for the organization" is equal to 3.41, i.e. the relative weight is 68.20%, and this means that there is high approval by the sample members of this paragraph.

The researchers attribute this to: The associations' keenness to have strong relations with the authorities concerned with project financing in order to facilitate access to them, but in light of the Israeli blockade and the Palestinian division, negatively affected the projects brought to the Gaza Strip.

In general, it can be said that the mean of the creative behavior scale "is 3.94, that is, the relative weight of 78.99%, and this means that there is a high agreement by the individuals of the sample on the paragraphs of this measure.

The researchers attribute this to the keenness of the associations in the Gaza Strip to consolidate the relationship between all its employees and improve the language of communication and communication, as well as the introduction of modern technology and the use of computers instead of using paper writing, and to follow e-mail as a substitute for paper correspondence in order to advance the work of the associations and keep pace with the rapid scientific and technological development of In order to carry out the assigned tasks very quickly, these results agreed with some studies such as (Al-Mishout, 2011) study. There is a significant effect of participation in decision-making on administrative creativity. (Al-Zoubi and Al-Azab, 2005) study that evaluating workers for tuberculosis as creative was positive, the study (Simon, 2006) the institutions seeking excellence in the need to spread the culture of creativity inside.

Hypotheses Test:

Ho 1: There is a correlation at (0.05) between the clarity of vision and creative behavior in NGOs.

To test this hypothesis, the "Pearson correlation coefficient" test was used, and the following table illustrates this.

Table 12: Correlation coefficient between vision clarity and creative behavior

Independent Variable	Creative Behavior	
	R	(Sig.)
Clarity Vision	.595	*0.000

* Correlation statistically at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$).

The previous table shows that the correlation coefficient equals .595, and that the probability value (Sig.) Equals 0,000 and is less than the significance level of 0.05. This indicates a statistically significant relationship between clarity of vision and creative behavior among civil servants working in Gaza Strip.

We also note from the previous table that there is a statistically significant relationship between clarity of vision and creative behavior, and this confirms the validity of the hypothesis.

The researchers attribute this to the keenness of the associations in Gaza Strip to be quick-wise in its work and its selection of distinguished work staff, especially that its work is charitable with a view to providing services to members of society from the target groups and a sense of social responsibility in achieving its goals as soon as possible and at the lowest possible costs and costs, as well as achieving the highest possible levels From the satisfaction of the beneficiaries compared to the competitors, the associations have essential capabilities, especially the human element who possesses the superior competitive advantage by

implementing the basic activities in the association, giving a mental plan about the awareness of future events, and the clarity of the vision of the association and For the speed necessary to implement and enjoy the required stability in investing and exploiting the available opportunities, and contributing to achieving the results and outputs of the work collectively, providing access to information to employees and maintaining them, and involving them significantly in planning, implementation, actions and participation in making decisions in the association, and adopting the method of dialogue and discussion between all parties responsible for Implement strategies that encourage initiatives and exchange ideas related to their implementation and presented through the various units and departments of work within the association.

These results were consistent with some studies such as (Al-Zabin, 2013). There is a relationship and impact of the characteristics of strategic information in achieving strategic agility, Al-Sane, 2013 study. There is a statistically significant effect of strategic agility with its variables in achieving organizational effectiveness with its creative variables. A study (2013, Abu Radi,) There is a relationship between variables of clarity of vision and variables of competitiveness, study (Al-Khawalada and Al-Hunaity, 2008) and a relationship between the dimensions of vision and creative behavior.

Ho 2: There are statistically significant differences at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the responses of the sample opinions about clarity of vision according to the following variables (gender, age group, number of years of service, educational qualification and specialization).

This hypothesis is divided into the following subsets of hypotheses:

1. There are statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the responses of the sample opinions on clarity of vision according to the gender variable.

To verify the validity of the hypothesis, the differences between the averages of the sample members were calculated according to the gender variable using the test (T) and the following table shows that:

Table 13: mean averages, standard deviations, and "T" value for clarity of vision due to the gender variable

Field	Gender	The Number	The Average	Standard Deviation	T Value	Significance Level	Significance
Clarity Vision	Male	145	3.8467	.71342	-3.167*	0.002	Significant
	Female	150	4.0696	.47586			

"T" value is statistically significant at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$).

The previous table indicates that there are statistically significant differences in clarity of vision due to the gender variable in clarity of vision in favor of females, where the calculated value (T) was greater than the value of (T) tabular.

The researchers attribute this to the study community who are from the distinguished category in the field of associations and they are fully aware of the importance of agility in the work of the institution and their ability to assume responsibility for providing services to beneficiaries to the fullest while females find it is more interested to prove themselves that they are the wall and the best in particular By obtaining projects that benefit the community to the fullest.

This study differed with the study (Ubaidah, 2016) and the study (Jad Allah, 2016). There are no statistically significant differences for the study variables.

2. There are statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between responses of the sample opinions about clarity of vision according to the age group variable.

To test this hypothesis, a "mono-contrast" test was used, and the following table illustrates this.

Table 14: Results of the "mono-variance" test - for the age group variable

Field	Averages				Test Value	Probability Value (Sig.)
	Less Than 30 Years	30 - Less Than 40 Years	40- Less Than 50 Years	50 Years And Over		
Clarity Vision	4.0044	3.9552	3.9125	3.8758	0.419	0.739

* The difference between the meanings is statistically significant at the significance level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$).

From the results shown in the previous table, the following can be concluded:

It was found that the probability value (Sig.) Corresponding to the "mono-variance" test was higher than the significance level 0.05 in the clarity of vision, thus it can be concluded that there are no statistically significant differences between the averages of the study sample estimates about the clarity of vision attributed to the age group variable.

The researchers attribute this to the fact that employees in the associations in Gaza Strip have the ability to deal with all external institutions that finance the project, through seminars held by those institutions supporting all associations operating in Gaza Strip, regardless of the age group, it gives information related to writing projects and training courses for all without exception.

These results were consistent with some studies such as (Khalaf, 2010), that there were no statistically significant differences according to the variable of the age group.

3. There are statistically significant differences at the level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the responses of the sample opinions about the clarity of vision according to the variable of the educational qualification.

To test this hypothesis, a "mono-contrast" test was used, and the following table illustrates this.

Table 15: Results of the "mono-variance" test - for the variable of the qualification level

Field	Averages			Test Value	Probability Value (Sig.)
	Diploma	Bachelor's Degree	Postgraduate		
Clarity Vision	3.9505	3.9996	3.8156	1.705	0.184

* The difference between the meanings is statistically significant at the significance level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$).

From the results shown in the previous table, the following can be concluded:

It was found that the probability value (Sig.) Corresponding to the "mono-variance" test was higher than the significance level 0.05 in the clarity of vision, and thus it can be concluded that there are no statistically significant differences between the averages of the study sample estimates about this field due to the educational qualification.

The researchers attribute this to the fact that all employees in the associations in Gaza Strip seek to develop their expertise through a commitment to attend training courses held by international institutions for all associations, regardless of their educational qualifications and provide guidance and guidance to them through training courses and focus on how to use the various methods in writing participation, Which in turn leads to the success of projects, which, through those courses that are given to all associations without exception, regardless of the educational qualification, drives them all to show their accomplishments and works in order to prove that they are more worthy than others in the work of institutions.

These results agreed with some studies as a study (Jad Allah, 2016). There are no statistically significant differences between the averages of the study sample estimates about this field due to the scientific qualification and differed with the study (Ubaidah, 2016) in the presence of statistically significant differences between the averages of the study sample estimates. About this field attributed to the educational qualification.

4. There are statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) level between responses of the sample opinions on clarity of vision according to the specialty variable.

To test this hypothesis, a "mono-contrast" test was used, and the following table illustrates this.

Table 16: Results of the "mono-variance" test - for the specialty variable

Field	Averages					Test Value	Probability Value (Sig.)
	Human Sciences	Administrative And Financial Sciences	Engineering Sciences	Public Relations and Media	Other Specialties		
Clarity Vision	4.0333	4.0120	3.8754	4.0317	3.8093	0.1773	0.134

* The difference between the meanings is statistically significant at the significance level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$).

From the results shown in the previous table, the following can be concluded:

It was found that the probability value (Sig.) Corresponding to the mono-contrast test showed that there were no differences in the clarity of vision due to the specialty variable.

The researchers attribute this to the instructions issued by the competent ministry that would lead to an increase in employees 'creativity and personal behavior, in addition to that, administrative work is sometimes considered specialization and field, which is important in improving the work of the institution and ensuring the quality of work in it.

The researchers attribute this to the fact that these specialties play a fundamental role in responding quickly to changes and emergency events in light of the instability of the situation in Gaza Strip.

5. There are statistically significant differences at the level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the responses of the sample opinions on clarity of vision according to the variable of the number of years of service.

To test this hypothesis, a "mono-contrast" test was used, and the following table illustrates this.

Table 17: Results of the "mono-variance" test - for the variable number of years of service

Field	Averages				Test Value	Probability Value (Sig.)
	Less than 5 years	From 5 to 10 years	From 10 to 15 years	Over 15 years		
Clarity Vision	4.0151	4.0194	3.8253	3.9184	1.547	0.202

* The difference between the meanings is statistically significant at the significance level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$).

From the results shown in the previous table, the following can be concluded:

It was found that the probability value (Sig.) Corresponding to the mono-contrast test showed that there were no differences in visibility, due to the variable number of years of service.

The researchers attribute this to the fact that experience has a fundamental role for entrepreneurs in the associations in Gaza Strip and encourage members of the study sample on entrepreneurship to take responsibility and set goals with great accuracy and make timely decisions.

The researchers attribute this to the trend of employees in the associations in Gaza Strip to practice various activities in order to maintain the survival of the association in light of the rapid response to changes and emergency events in light of the presence of a turbulent and accelerating environment in the association.

Ho 3: There are statistically significant differences at the level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the responses of the sample opinions on creative behavior according to the following variables (gender, age group, educational qualification, specialization and number of years of service).

This hypothesis is divided into the following subsets of hypotheses:

1. There are statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the responses of the sample opinions on creative behavior according to the gender variable.

To verify the validity of the hypothesis, the differences between the averages of the sample members were calculated using the T-test for the independent samples according to the gender variable and the following table shows that:

Table 18: Standard Averages, Standard Deviations, and a Value of the Creative Behavior Scale Attributed to the Gender Variable

Field	Gender	The Number	The Average	Standard Deviation	T Value	Significance Level
The total score for creative behavior	Male	147	3.8928	.59852	-1.741	0.083
	Female	151	4.0049	.50807		

• The value of "t" is statistically significant at the significance level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$).

The previous table indicates that there were no statistically significant differences in the dimensions of the scale due to the gender variable in the overall degree of the scale where the calculated value of (T) was greater than the value of (T) tabular.

The researchers attribute this to the fact that the members of the study sample generally face the same conditions in terms of leadership excellence, excellence of employees in it, excellence in planning and excellence in creative behavior, since these fields are seen by association managers because the aforementioned fields are concerned with the performance of employees in associations and they all strive to raise themselves at all levels of the social type.

2. There are statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the responses of the sample opinions on creative behavior according to the age group variable.

To test this hypothesis, a "mono-contrast" test was used, and the following table illustrates this.

Table 19: Results of the "mono-variance" test - for the age group variable

Field	Averages				Test Value	Probability Value (Sig.)
	Less Than 30 Years	30 - Less Than 40 Years	40- Less Than 50 Years	50 Years And Over		
Total Score	4.0176	3.9074	3.9783	3.7817	1.480	0.220

* The difference between the two meanings is statistically significant at the significance level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$).

From the results shown in the previous table, the following can be concluded:

It was found that the probability value (Sig.) Corresponding to the "mono-variance" test was higher than the significance level 0.05 for the total degree of creative behavior, and thus it can be concluded that there are no statistically significant differences between the averages of the study sample estimates about this field due to the age group.

The researchers attribute this to the majority of the associations in Gaza Strip, who are moving properly around the selection of people with credibility and are well aware of the work of the institutions.

These results agreed with some studies as a study (Khalaf, 2010), as there are no statistically significant differences between the averages of the study sample estimates about this field due to the age group.

3. There are statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the responses of the sample opinions on creative behavior according to the variable of the educational qualification.

To test this hypothesis, a "mono-contrast" test was used, and the following table illustrates this.

Table 20: Results of the "mono-variance" test - for the variable of the qualification level

Field	Averages			Test Value	Probability Value (Sig.)
	Diploma	Bachelor's Degree	Postgraduate		
The total score for creative behavior	3.9518	3.9637	3.8916	0.320	0.726

* The difference between the two meanings is statistically significant at the significance level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$).

From the results shown in the previous table, the following can be concluded:

It was found that the probability value (Sig.) Corresponding to the "mono-variance" test is higher than the significance level 0.05 for all dimensions and for the overall degree of strategic agility, and thus it can be concluded that there are no statistically significant differences between the averages of the study sample estimates about this field due to the educational qualification.

The researchers attribute this to the association managers' implementation of the instructions, regulations, and regulations of all employees and informing them of it. These laws apply to all employees, whether employees are bachelor's or graduate studies, their opinion is not affected by the difference in the degree and this reflected positively on the progress of the societies' work in Gaza Strip for each of them.

4. There are statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the responses of the sample opinions on creative behavior according to the specialty variable.

To test this hypothesis, a "mono-contrast" test was used, and the following table illustrates this.

Table 21: Results of the "mono-variance" test - for the specialty variable

Field	Averages					Test Value	Probability Value (Sig.)
	Human Sciences	Administrative And Financial Sciences	Engineering Sciences	Public Relations And Media	Other Specialties		
The total score for creative behavior	3.9870	4.0090	3.7800	2.9592	3.8814	1.166	0.326

* The difference between the two meanings is statistically significant at the significance level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$).

From the results shown in the previous table, the following can be concluded:

It was found that the probabilistic value (Sig.) Corresponding to the "mono-variance" test is higher than the significance level 0.05 for the total degree of creative behavior, thus concluding that there are no statistically significant differences between the averages of the study sample estimates about this field due to the variable of specialization.

Researchers attribute this to the application of associations managers in Gaza Strip to the instructions, regulations and regulations of all employees and inform them about it, and these laws apply to all employees, whether employees are from the literary or scientific specialization, the managers' opinion is not affected by the difference in degree and specialization, and this reflected positively on the progress of the institutional planning of the associations for each of them.

5. There are statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the responses of the sample opinions on creative behavior according to the variable of the number of years of service.

To test this hypothesis, a "mono-contrast" test was used, and the following table illustrates this.

Table 22: Results of the "mono-variance" test - for the variable number of years of service

Field	Averages				Test Value	Probability Value (Sig.)
	Less than 5 years	From 5 - 10 years	From 10 - 15 years	Over 15 years		
The total score for creative behavior	4.0277	3.9885	3.7724	3.9587	3.093*	0.027

* The difference between the two meanings is statistically significant at the significance level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$).

From the results shown in the previous table, the following can be concluded:

It was found that the probabilistic value (Sig.) Corresponding to the "mono-variance" test is less than the significance level of 0.05 for the total degree of creative behavior and thus it can generally be concluded that there are statistically significant differences between the averages of the study sample estimates, the measure of scale attributable to the variable number of years of service.

The researchers attribute this to the fact that most of the employees in the universities in Gaza Strip have previous experience in the field of groups and attend seminars and meetings held by donor institutions in Gaza Strip.

These results were consistent with some studies such as (Al-Khawalada and Al-Hunaity, 2008). There are statistically significant differences between the averages of the study sample measurements, the measure is attributed to the variable number of years of service. To find the difference trend, LSD test was used as in the following table

Table 23: LSD test results to compare average service years for the total degree of creative behavior

Categories	The Difference Between The Averages			
	Less than 5 years	From 5 - 10 years	From 10 - 15 years	Over 15 years
Less than 5 years				
From 5 - 10 years	-0.07224			
From 10 - 15 years	*-0.27240	*-0.20016		
Over 15 years	-0.12738	-0.05514	0.14501	-

* The difference between the two meanings is statistically significant at the significance level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$).

The previous table shows the results of the LSD test for comparing the average income categories of the degree for creative behavior, where the results show that there are statistically significant differences between the averages of the number of service years (10-less than 15 years) and the number of years of service (5-less than 10 years) the number of years of service (Less than 5

years) This is in favor of the number of years of service (5-less than 10 years) and the number of years of service (less than 5 years), meaning that less experience is more creative behavior.

The researchers attribute this to the fact that the majority of employees in the associations in the youth category find them more enthusiastic about the work, and this, in turn, positively reflected the progress of the Foundation's work in all fields.

Results

- There is high agreement with the dimension of vision, as the relative weight has reached 79.20%.
- There is a high agreement with the creative behavior scale as the relative weight is 78.99%.
- There is a statistically significant relationship between vision clarity and creative behavior.
- There are statistically significant differences in clarity of vision due to the gender variable in favor of females.
- There were no statistically significant differences between the averages of the study sample estimates about the visibility due to the age group variable.
- There were no statistically significant differences between the averages of the study sample estimates about clarity of vision due to the educational qualification.
- There were no statistically significant differences between the averages of the study sample estimates in the clarity of vision due to the specialty variable.
- There are no statistically significant differences between the averages of the study sample estimates and the clarity of vision due to the variable of the number of years of service.
- There were no statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the responses of the sample opinions on creative behavior according to the gender variable.
- There were no statistically significant differences between the averages of the study sample estimates on creative behavior attributed to the age group.
- There were no statistically significant differences between the averages of the study sample estimates on creative behavior attributable to the educational qualification.
- There were no statistically significant differences between the averages of the study sample estimates on creative behavior attributable to the specialty.
- There are statistically significant differences between the averages of the study sample estimates about the creative behavior of the scale due to the variable number of years of service.
- There are statistically significant differences between the averages of the number of years of service (10-less than 15 years) and the number of years of service (5-less than 10 years) the number of years of service (less than 5 years) in favor of the number of years of service (5-less than 10 Years) and the number of years of service (less than 5 years), meaning that less experience is more creative behavior.

Recommendations

Based on its findings, the following recommendations can be made:

- The need for civil organizations in Gaza Strip to seek funding from foreign countries in order to provide a self-income for the association to face crises and give them independence in order to preserve them to play their role in society.
- The need for civil organizations in Gaza Strip to have a written strategic plan used as a guide for employees working at different administrative levels to achieve the organization's goals and vision
- Working to employ NGOs in Gaza Strip, with their experience in funded projects, to find a self-source for the association.
- The necessity of creating competitive and stimulating programs between universities in the field of computerizing services and developing them so that they become more superior and faster at work.
- The use of consultative bodies, including experts and academics, in the field of writing projects and benefiting from them, whether they are related to the educational, agricultural and health aspects, in a way that serves the infrastructure of Gaza Strip.
- Work to spread awareness among employees about the necessity of their participation in evaluating, identifying and developing services by submitting their proposals to the competent authorities.
- The necessity of setting a training program for employees in associations in Gaza Strip in the field of information in various institutions on the safety, security and archiving of information
- The necessity of holding meetings and workshops with the local community, and this helps them to define the community's needs.

- Determining the possibility of accessing data in accordance with the powers system, by establishing internal regulations to that effect.
- The need for NGOs in Gaza Strip to use their legal right to own income-generating projects to meet the needs of NGOs.

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